

УЎТ:634.22

INFLUENCE OF FORMATION METHODS ON PLUM YIELD AND TRADITIONAL FRUIT CHARACTERISTICS

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Annotation: The article considers the yield of plum varieties, fruit quality, marketability, formed in 4 different ways. When choosing shaping methods, 4 new modern methods were used, tested on 3 plum varieties, and the influence of different shaping methods on the growing season was determined.

Key words: varieties, yield, fruit size, fruit weight, molding methods.

ШАКЛ БЕРИШ УСУЛЛАРИНИ ОЛХЎРИ ҲОСИЛДОРЛИГИ ВА МЕВАЛАРИНИНГ ТОВАРЛИЛИК ХУСУСИЯТЛАРИГА ТАЪСИРИ

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Аннотация. Мақолада 4 хил усулларда шакл берилган олхўри навларининг ҳосилдорлиги, меваларнинг сифати, товарлилик хусусиятлари

хақида сўз юритилган. Шакл бериш усуллари танлашда хозирги кундаги замонавий янги 4 та усуллар қўлланилган бўлиб олхўрининг 3 та навларида синаб кўрилган ҳамда турли шакллар бериш усуллари вегетация даврининг ўтишига таъсири аниқланган.

Калит сўзлар: навлар, ҳосилдорлик, меваларнинг йириклиги, меваларнинг оғирлиги, шакл бериш усуллари.

ВЛИЯНИЕ СПОСОБОВ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ НА УРОЖАЙНОСТЬ СЛИВЫ И ТРАДИЦИОННЫЕ ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКИ ПЛОДОВ

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Аннотация: В статье рассмотрена урожайность сортов сливы, качество плодов, товарность, формируемая 4 различными способами. При выборе способов формирования использовали 4 новых современных способа, испытанных на 3 сортах сливы, и определяли влияние разных способов формирования на вегетационный период.

Ключевые слова: сорта, урожайность, размер плодов, масса плодов, способы формовки.

Currently, the world's annual plum production produces 12,063,776 tons of plums. Of these, Chinese plums account for 6,676,142 tons per year. Romania ranks

second with 512,975 tons per year. The Russian Federation ranks 13th with 164,602 tons. 14,483 hectares[7].

Plum trees are one of the fruit trees that can adapt well to almost all regions of Uzbekistan. The amount of yield in the gardens depends not only on the correct selection of varieties, but also on the effective conduct of agro-technical measures, the width of the row spacing, the orderly placement and distance of trees [2]. Plum trees are one of the fruit trees that can adapt well to almost all regions of Uzbekistan. The amount of yield in the gardens depends not only on the correct selection of varieties, but also on the effective conduct of agro-technical measures, the width of the row spacing, the orderly placement and distance of trees [2].

Mistakes in the organization of plum orchards, as a result of thick planting of trees and their care, including improper shaping, can adversely affect the quantity and quality of fruit [5, 3].

- Research "Methods and programs for the study of fruit, berry and plum varieties" (Oryol 1999) [6] and methods of calculations and phenological observations in experiments with fruit and berry plants, developed by the All-Russian Research Institute of Fruit Selection. H.Ch.Buriev 2014) [1]. In experiments, the effect of different methods of shaping plum varieties Leto, Burton, Chyornaya bagira on fruit quality and yield was studied. Forming methods are implemented in 5 variants, which are 1-вариант (Австрия бутаси) шакл бериш усули

Option 2 (Rare tier) shaping method

Option 3 (KGB (Kim Green Bush)) shaping method

Option 4 (Vase) Shaping Method (Standard)

Option 5 Figure is not given

According to the results of the study, in 2021, when the control variant of the Leto navigator of the plum is formed by the method of "Kosasimon", the average yield per bush is 17.85 kg. The average yield was 142.8 ts / ha per hectare. Also, the

weight of 100 fruits was 7.3 kg, the average weight of 1 fruit was 60.2 grams and the weight of the largest fruit was 76 grams.

Option 1 When formed by the method of "Austrian bush", the average yield is 14.9 kg per bush. The average yield was 119.2 ts / ha per hectare. Also, the weight of 100 fruits was 7.17 kg, the average weight of 1 fruit was 61.4 grams and the weight of the largest fruit was 77 grams.

Option 2 When formed by the method of "Austrian bush", the average yield is 16.6 kg per bush. The average yield was 133.1 ts / ha per hectare. The weight of 100 fruits was 7.24 kg, the average weight of 1 fruit was 63.2 grams and the weight of the largest fruit was 81 grams.

Option 3 When formed by the method of "KGB Kim Green bush", the average yield is 11.0 kg per bush. averaged 88.24 ts / ha per hectare. Also, the weight of 100 fruits was 7.06 kg, the average weight of 1 fruit was 58.6 grams and the weight of the largest fruit was 77 grams.

When the control variant of the plum Burton navigation is formed by the method of «Kosasimon», the average yield is 15.04 kg per bush. The average yield was 120.3 ts / ha per hectare. The weight of 100 fruits was 6.3 kg, the average weight of 1 fruit was 59.2 grams and the weight of the largest fruit was 80 grams.

Option 1 When formed by the method of "Austrian bush", the average yield is 14.08 kg per bush. The average yield was 112.6 ts / ha per hectare. The weight of 100 fruits was 7.44 kg, the average weight of 1 fruit was 65.4 grams and the weight of the largest fruit was 77 grams.

Option 2 When formed by the method of "Austrian bush", the average yield is 14.24 kg per bush. The average yield was 113.9 ts / ha per hectare. The weight of 100 fruits was 6.64 kg, the average weight of 1 fruit was 62.4 grams and the weight of the largest fruit was 77 grams.

Option 3 The average yield is 10.8 kg per bush when formed using the KGB Kim Green Bush method. The average yield was 86.5 ts / ha per hectare. Also, the

weight of 100 fruits is 6.84 kg, 1 fruit the average weight was 64.6 grams and the largest fruit weighed 81 grams.

In the unformed variant, the average yield is 12.8 kg per bush. The average yield was 102.8 ts / ha per hectare. The weight of 100 fruits was 3.76 kg, the average weight of 1 fruit was 30.8 grams and the weight of the largest fruit was 43 grams.

The average yield of a bush is 16.36 kg. averaged 130.8 ts / ha per hectare. Also, the weight of 100 fruits was 5.66 kg, the average weight of 1 fruit was 60.8 grams and the weight of the largest fruit was 80 grams.

Option 1 When formed by the method of "Austrian bush", the average yield is 14.8 kg per bush. The average yield was 118.7 ts / ha per hectare. The weight of 100 fruits was 6.42 kg, the average weight of 1 fruit was 63.2 grams and the weight of the largest fruit was 80 grams.

Table 1

Yields and fruit quality indicators of plum varieties formed in different ways.

Options	Average yield per bush, kg	Yield per 1 ha area, ts	Fruits in 1 kg number	100 fruits weight, kg	1 fruit average mass, g	largest fruit, g
Leto navi						
Option 1 (Austrian bush)	14,9	119,2	15	7,17	61,4	77
Option 2 (Rare Tier)	16,6	133,1	13,8	7,24	63,2	81
Option 3 (KGB Kim Green bush)	11,0	88,24	14,8	7,06	58,6	77
Option 4 (control Kosasimon)	17,85	142,8	14	7,3	60,2	76
Option 5 (Not Formed)	13,8	110,4	23,2	4,02	32,2	43
Berton navi						
Option 1 (Austrian bush)	14,08	112,6	13,2	7,44	65,4	77
Option 2 (Rare Tier)	14,24	113,9	16	6,64	62,4	77
Option 3 (KGB Kim Green bush)	10,8	86,5	16,8	6,84	64,6	81
Option 4 (Kosasimon)	15,04	120,3	17,2	6,3	59,2	80
Option 5 (Not Formed)	12,8	102,8	27	3,76	30,8	43

Chyorniy bagira						
Option 1 (Austrian bush)	14,8	118,7	13,8	6,42	63,2	80
Option 2 (Rare Tier)	15,36	122,8	15,2	6,24	62,8	78
Option 3 (KGB Kim Green bush)	11,6	92,8	15,4	5,96	64,8	79
Option 4 (Kosasimon)	16,36	130,8	17,2	5,66	60,8	80
Option 5 (Not Formed)	13,46	107,6	28,6	4,04	30,8	43

Option 2 When formed by the method of "Austrian bush", the average yield is 15.36 kg per bush. The average yield was 122.8 ts / ha per hectare. Also, the weight of 100 fruits was 6.24 kg, the average weight of 1 fruit was 62.8 grams and the weight of the largest fruit was 78 grams.

Option 3 The average yield is 11.6 kg per bush when formed using the KGB Kim Green Bush method. The average yield was 92.8 ts / ha per hectare. The weight of 100 fruits was 5.96 kg, the average weight of 1 fruit was 64.8 grams and the weight of the largest fruit was 79 grams

In the unformed variant, the average yield is 13.46 kg per bush. The average yield was 107.6 ts / ha per hectare. Also, the weight of 100 fruits was 4.04 kg, the average weight of 1 fruit was 30.8 grams and the weight of the largest fruit was 43 grams.

Conclusion. The high yield of fruits in the formation of plum varieties in different ways, with the size of the fruit is as follows:

1. Option 2 in the Leto variety was distinguished by its sparse-layered shaping method with high yields and fruit size.
2. Option 3 of the Burton variety was distinguished by the yield and size of the fruit in the KGB Kim Green bush shaping method.
3. Option 1 of the Chyorniy bagira variety was distinguished by its yield and fruit size in the Austrian bush shaping method.

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